

ARTS

ART STUDIES IMPORTANT FEATURES OF THE CONTEXTUALIST METHOD

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Abstract

The methodological transformations that have taken place in the field of ethnomusicology and folklore studies in recent decades clearly demonstrate that context is gradually emerging as a fundamental axis for the perception, analysis, and comprehensive interpretation of musical and folklore phenomena. In modern scientific discourse, it is no longer viewed as a mere external environment or supporting framework that complements the main material, but is perceived as an ontological environment within which all musical and folklore processes are formed, operate, and constantly reproduced. The article is dedicated to the theoretical justification of the contextualist method and the principles of its practical application.

Keywords: ethnomusicology, folklore, methodology, contextualist, supporting framework

INTRODUCTION

As is known, folklore cannot be perceived outside its living environment: it exists not as a "closed" and finished creation, but as an open and continuous act of communication. The fundamentals of the context-centered method were formed in sociology and ethnography. They were first formulated most clearly in the works of the Polish-born English ethnographer and sociologist Bronislaw Kaspar Malinowski (1884–1942) "The Problem of the Meaning of Primitive Languages" /1923/ and "Coral Gardens and Their Magic" /1935/. Here the principle of "context of situation" was formed, according to which any cultural or linguistic manifestation receives its full meaning not from its internal structure itself, but from the natural environment of its existence - in the context of social interaction, practical goals and cultural belonging. This methodological revolution, one of the key pillars of Malinowski's scientific legacy, opposed the static approach of viewing language or culture as an isolated, self-regulating system, emphasizing that language is first and foremost a "form of action."

In Bronislaw Malinowski's work "The Problem of the Meaning of Primitive Languages", the understanding of the meaning of language is based on the principle that linguistic units cannot be interpreted independently, separated from the life situations in which they are used. The author consistently opposes linguistic approaches that seek meaning within words or sentences and view language as an autonomous system. At the heart of his theory is the belief that the true meaning of a linguistic expression is revealed only in the conditions of speech use, within the framework of a social and operational context.

This position is clearly expressed in Malinowski's following formulation: "A word receives its meaning from the context of the situation in which it is uttered" (Malinowski, 1923, p. 305). Based on this statement, Malinowski introduces the concept of "situational

context", which is one of the fundamental concepts of his theory. In his understanding, context includes the physical environment, social relations, the positions of the speakers, their goals and the actions taking place at a given time. Malinowski emphasizes: "The situation in which words are uttered can never be ignored without losing the real meaning of the expression" (Malinowski, 1923, p. 306). This statement confirms that context is not an external complement to a linguistic expression, but an integral part of its semantic structure.

For Malinowski, language does not serve exclusively to describe reality or to transmit information. He views it as an integral part of human activity, emphasizing that speech is closely related to action. He formulates this idea as follows: "Speech is essentially related to action, and only in relation to action can its meaning be explained" (Malinowski, 1923, p. 308). With this approach, linguistic communication acquires a functional character, and meaning becomes the result of social practice.

Through numerous ethnographic examples presented in the work, Malinowski shows that the speech forms used in "primitive" societies are often not subject to literal translation. Their meaning is determined not by the dictionary meaning of the words, but by the given cultural and operational context. He describes short phrases and calls uttered during work processes, which do not convey new information, but ensure the organization of joint activity and social synchronization. Regarding such speech forms, Malinowski notes that they "become meaningless if they are separated from the action in which they appear" (Malinowski, 1923, pp. 309–310). Here it becomes clear that linguistic meaning is also formed through its function.

The primacy of context is also most clearly expressed in Malinowski's idea of phatic communication. He emphasizes that some forms of

language exist not for the purpose of transmitting ideas, but for the purpose of establishing and maintaining communicative contact. According to Malinowski, phatic communication “does not transmit ideas, but creates a sense of social presence and interconnectedness” (Malinowski, 1923, p. 314). Such speech can be fully understood only within the social and cultural environment in which it is used, since its meaning lies in the fact of communicative contact, and not in its information content.

The work “The Problem of the Meaning of Primitive Languages” forms the theoretical foundations of a context-centered understanding of language and creates important prerequisites for the further development of functional and social studies of language.

Bronislaw Malinowski's multi-volume work "Coral Gardens and Their Magic" is built on a detailed description of the social and magical system that developed around the economic activities of the Trobriand Islands, in particular gardening. Gardening work is never presented in Malinowski as a purely material production: it is perceived as a socially regulated process, each stage of which is accompanied by ritual actions and verbal forms. It is in this context that magical speech becomes one of the main mechanisms for organizing work, time, and social relations.

In the second volume of the work, Malinowski distinguishes different types of magic related to soil cultivation, sowing, crop preservation, and prevention of natural hazards. He shows that magic formulas are highly specialized and are used only at certain stages during the corresponding actions. According to Malinowski, the magic word “is not uttered arbitrarily, but is associated with a certain moment, place, and actor of the action” (Malinowski, 1935, vol. II, p. 52).

Malinowski considers the content of magic formulas from the point of view of function, noting that many formulas have archaic, sometimes even untranslatable vocabulary, the meaning of which is not fully understood by the speakers. However, this circumstance does not reduce the effectiveness of the formulas, since their power is determined not by the meaning of the words, but by the manner of their execution. He writes: "The effective power of magical speech lies not in the explicable meaning of what is said, but in the traditionally established form of its utterance" (Malinowski, 1935, vol. II, p. 59).

This observation is particularly important from an ethnomusicological perspective, as it shows that the sound organization—rhythm, intonation, repetition—are factors that create meaning. Malinowski describes the vocalization patterns of magical formulas, noting that they are often pronounced with a uniform tempo, with pronounced accents, and with a repetitive structure. In the second volume of his work, he describes in detail the formulas of Trobriand Island horticultural magic as vocalized, performative actions whose meaning is conditioned by the phonetic form. For example, in the case of the magic words related to the planting of yams, he notes that the magician pronounces the formula with a uniform, almost song-like intonation, without verbal expressive fluctuations,

since “the speech must flow continuously, like the action it accompanies” (Malinowski, 1935, vol. II, pp. 64–65). These formulas are uttered at a constant tempo and are never sped up or slowed down, regardless of external conditions, which indicates that rhythmic stability is perceived as a prerequisite for the effectiveness of magic.

Another specific example is given by Malinowski in his description of the magic words related to the growth of gardens, where he emphasizes the obligatory nature of repetition. He notes that some formulas must be repeated in the same sequence and with the same pronunciation several times, and this repetition cannot be shortened or changed in any case. Malinowski specifically notes that “repetition in magic speech ensures not memory, but continuity and effectiveness of action” (Malinowski, 1935, vol. II, p. 70), thereby showing that phonetic repetition has a functional role and directly affects the perceived result of the ritual. According to him, this repetitive structure forms a special rhythmic flow of speech, which cannot be replaced by free verbal expression.

The author also touches on the synchronization of speech and physical action. Malinowski describes how, in horticultural magic, speech is uttered in a rhythm that coincides with the movements of cultivating the soil: digging, planting, or leveling the soil. He notes: “The pronunciation of the formula is not interrupted as long as the action continues and the rhythm of the speech is subordinated to the process of work” (Malinowski, 1935, pp. 72-73). Malinowski also pays attention to the role of the performer. Magic formulas cannot be uttered by just anyone; they belong to specific social actors whose authority and position in the community guarantee the effect of the word. According to him, “the power of the formula is inseparable from the person who is authorized to pronounce it” (Malinowski, 1935, p. 65). This once again demonstrates that the oral tradition here acts as a socially regulated performance act, which is consistent with the approach according to which the identity of the performer is an integral part of musical meaning.

He criticizes attempts that are limited to the textual fixation of formulas without a description of the conditions of their implementation. In Malinowski's formulation, "speech without a description of movements, gestures, and action turns into a dead text" (Malinowski, 1935, vol. II, p. 62).

The importance of Bronislaw Malinowski's methodological approach is due to the fact that over time it significantly transformed the scientific perspective on the study of cultural phenomena, shifting it towards living experience and social action.

This method had a profound and lasting impact on various branches of cultural studies, especially ethnomusicology, where the contextual thinking proposed by Malinowski was reformulated as an independent methodological direction about three decades later. The context-centered school that emerged in the second half of the twentieth century, largely based on anthropological operational approaches, began to view song folklore as a social activity that exists in a specific cultural environment and performs certain social functions. One of the most

influential representatives of this trend was the British ethnomusicologist John Blacking, whose work "How Musical Is Man?" became a turning point, summarizing and theoretically clarifying the approaches that originated in Malinowski's anthropological observations.

John Blacking's *How Musical Is Man?* represents a theoretical shift in ethnomusicology that places the idea of context at the heart of the study of music, redefining the nature of music as a form of human activity. He takes folk music out of the narrow confines of "work," "creation," or "style" and places it at the center of human experience and social life. Blacking's main claim is that song-making is, first and foremost, human behavior.

Blacking emphasizes that song organization is never a purely mechanical process. It is shaped by cultural values, social relations, worldviews, and modes of communication. This is where his approach is closely linked to contextual thinking. He explicitly contrasts the approach that analyzes folk song only at the level of its internal structure, writing: "The structures of music cannot be fully understood without an understanding of the social relations that create them" (Blacking, 1973, p. 54).

John Blacking's African fieldwork, particularly his long and detailed study of the musical culture of the Venda people of South Africa, formed the core of his theoretical approach. Studying the songs, rhythmic games, dance accompaniments of the Venda community and their use in various social situations, Blacking came to the conclusion that musical structures that seem simple, sometimes even monotonous, on the surface cannot be evaluated by purely morphological or phonetic criteria. They carry a condensed expression of social experience, relationships and value systems. Blacking specifically emphasizes that the sound repetition, limited intonational material or rhythmic simplicity in the music of the Venda people do not indicate a lack of musical "development", but are due to the communicative and social organization of the given community. He writes: "What may seem to the outside observer to be musical simplicity is often the expression of a highly complex system of social meanings within the given culture."

This observation allows Bleking to reinterpret the relationship between musical form and social content. In Venda musical practice, song and rhythm are not seen as independent artistic products, but as a form of action that regulates social relations, strengthens community cohesion and ensures the continuity of experience transmitted from generation to generation. In this regard, Bleking writes: "Musical structures cannot be fully understood without an analysis of the social relations in which they function." From an ethnomusicological perspective, this approach is of fundamental importance, since it confirms that the meaning-making function of music is formed not only by the internal patterns of sound organization, but by their combination with the social context.

Of particular methodological importance is Bleking's idea of the "universality of musicality." He argues that musical ability is a biological prerequisite that manifests itself in different ways in different

cultures, depending on the social environment and educational experience. This proposition allows him to redefine the concept of musical skill, taking it out of professional or elite circles and linking it to everyday social life. The early involvement of children in singing and rhythmic games in the musical practices of the Venda people is for Bleking living proof of this thesis.

Blacking's theoretical and methodological positions prepared the scientific platform on which the more systematic formulation of the context-centered direction of ethnomusicology was formed in the 1960s. One of the central figures of this direction was the American ethnomusicologist Alan P. Merriam, who, like Blacking, rejected a purely morphological or autonomous interpretation of music, but at the same time sought to transform these approaches into a clear structural model. If Blacking perceived music primarily as socially conditioned human behavior, then Merriam tried to theoretically systematize and methodologically formulate this idea.

Alan P. Merriam's *The Anthropology of Music* was a turning point in ethnomusicology because it was the first systematic definition of music as a cultural entity. Merriam's fundamental thesis was that the study of folk song could not be limited to the analysis of the vocal output, since the latter was only the surface layer of deeper social and ideological processes. In this regard, he wrote: "Music is a human behavior, and like any other behavior, it must be studied in a cultural context" (Merriam, 1964, p. 32). This thesis became the basis for Merriam's proposed three-level model, which includes musical ideas, musical behavior, and vocal output.

At the level of musical ideas, Merriam refers to the culturally constructed notions of music: who has the right to perform, and in what situations it is permissible or obligatory. For example, in many African societies, singing is not perceived as a separate art form, but as an integral part of work, ritual, or social interaction, which directly affects both performance forms and musical material. Merriam also cites examples from North American Indian cultures to show how musical ideas precede sound form. He notes that among some tribes, the "correct" performance of a song is determined not by intonational accuracy, but by ritual conformity and the social status of the performer. In this regard, he emphasizes that if a given person does not have the right to perform the song, then even a technically perfect performance is considered meaningless to the given community.

Merriam also refers to work songs, emphasizing that their musical structure is often extremely simple, with a limited intonation range and repetitive rhythms, but this simplicity is due not to creative limitations, but to functional necessity. The song here serves to synchronize work, regulate physical movements, and maintain cohesion. In this context, he writes: "What we call musical form is often directly determined by the function that music performs in society" (Merriam, 1964, p. 210).

Second, at the level of musical behavior, Merriam focuses on the actions by which a folk song is performed in society. This includes performance, participation, listening, and even the social rules that

regulate musical activity. He emphasizes that musical behavior is always socially constructed and reflects the internal relations of the community. As a striking example of social behavior, the author details the status of musicians among the Basongye people of Congo, where the musician, despite his important social role, is considered a representative of the "lower" stratum of society, endowed with special behavioral privileges, such as drunkenness or open criticism, which are forbidden to other members of the community. This argues that musical behavior is always socially constructed and reflects the internal relations of the community. In this regard, he notes: "Musical behavior is not a series of random actions, but a socially organized process" (Merriam, 1964, p. 33).

The third level, the sonic output, is the one that has been most frequently studied by traditional musicology. However, Merriam specifically emphasizes that it is this level that is most inadequately interpreted when separated from the previous two. He cites as an example the singing style of the Flathead Indians, where the high vocal tension, the sharp guttural sounds, and the abrupt melodic drops may seem incomprehensible to the outside observer or analyst. However, when this sonic structure is linked to the ideology of the given culture, it becomes clear that this "physical tension" in the voice directly reflects the Indians' ideas about spiritual power and the complexity of achieving personal visions. On this occasion, he writes: "The sound itself says nothing if we do not know what it means to the people who create it" (Merriam, 1964, p. 27).

The model developed by Alan Merriam, which viewed music as an interconnected whole of ideas, behavior, and sound, significantly expanded the role of context in ethnomusicological analysis, but at the same time left out one important issue: how meaning is formed during the communicative act itself. This questioning already went beyond the scope of musical structures or social functions and moved into the field of cultural communication. It is at this point that ethnomusicological thinking intersects with the theoretical approach of Dan Ben Amos.

Dan Ben-Amos's theoretical concept occupies a special place in the development of context-centered thinking, as he radically redefines folklore, moving it from a text to a performance and communicative event. In his article "Toward a Definition of Folklore in Context" (1971), Ben-Amos openly criticizes approaches that define it as a collection of material or oral works, ignoring their social function and performance environment, about which he writes as follows: "Folklore cannot be understood outside its living environment; it exists not as a 'closed' and finished work, but as an open and continuous act of communication" (Ben-Amos, "Definition of Folklore in Context", *Journal of American Folklore*, vol. 84, no. 331, 1971, p. 13).

Ben-Amos emphasizes that the study of folklore inevitably requires attention to the participants in the communication and their relationships. In this regard, he notes: "The study of folklore necessarily involves an analysis of the relationships between speaker, audience, and situation." (Ben-Amos, "Defining Folklore in

Context," *Journal of American Folklore*, vol. 84, no. 331, 1971, p. 14)

Ben-Amos's performative approach is most clearly articulated in another of his important articles, "The Role of Performance in Folklore" (1972), where he defines performance as the moment when a folkloric phenomenon actually comes into existence. He argues that it cannot exist independently of the act of performance, since it is in that act that linguistic or phonetic material, social roles, and situational conditions are combined. Ben-Amos writes: "Performance is the moment when folklore becomes a social reality" (Ben-Amos, "The Role of Performance in Folklore," *Journal of the Folklore Institute*, vol. 9, pp. 2–3, 1972, p. 113).

Dan Ben Amos's theoretical position is shaped not only by general anthropological observations, but also by his own fieldwork, in particular on the material of the oral culture of the West African Yoruba people. His works often feature examples of Yoruba praise speech and oral storytelling, through which he shows that folkloric meaning depends not on the text, but on the specific conditions of performance. For example, referring to oriks, personal and tribal praise utterances, Ben Amos notes that the same text can have different effects and meanings in different situations, depending on who is the performer, to whom the speech is addressed, and in what social environment it is heard. He emphasizes that oriks do not function as a "poem" in the literary sense, but as a social act that establishes or reconstructs social relations. In that context, he writes, "Folkloric expression derives its power not from linguistic form, but from the communicative situation" (Ben-Amos, "1971, p. 15).

Thus, Dan Ben Amos's theoretical position transforms context not into a set of external conditions, but into an active component of the meaning-making process. His works reinforce the idea in ethnomusicology that music and folkloric musical-verbal genres should be studied as live performance events, the meaning of which is always conditioned by social relations and the communicative situation. This theoretical revolution of Ben Amos also found a logical development in the work of the American philologist Alan Dundes (1934–2005), who enriched the context-centered method with a new structural emphasis, proposing a three-in-one model for the analysis of any folklore material: Texture, Text, and Context.

The logical continuation and simultaneous theoretical systematization of the performance-communicative approach formulated by Dan Ben Amos can be seen in the works of Alan Dundes, where the idea of context is transformed into a multilayered analytical methodology. Dundes' scientific goal was to propose an analytical structure that would allow for the simultaneous consideration of linguistic or phonetic form, performance features, and social environment. The central expression of his theoretical position is the article "Text, Texture, Text, and Context" (1964), where folklore material is presented as a three-level interconnected system. Dundes argues that the study of musical folklore cannot be limited to the content layer alone. In this regard, he writes: "Folklore cannot be understood only through the text, since the text acquires

meaning only in the relationship between its structure and context" (Dundes, *Texture, Text, and Context*, 1964, p. 253).

Conclusion

In the three-level model proposed by Dundes, the concept of texture refers to the phonological-performance layer: intonation, rhythm, pronunciation, repetition, and all those formal elements that are directly perceived at the auditory or visual level. The text includes the content structure: narrative units, the image system, and semantic layers, while the context defines the social and cultural environment in which the work is realized. Dundes emphasizes that these three levels are inseparable, and ignoring any of them leads to incomplete analysis.

Dundes's work also features the idea of variability as an indicator of vitality. He believes that each performance is a new reconstruction, and these variations are evidence of social adaptation and cultural continuity. In this regard, he notes: "Change is the essence of folklore, since it is evidence of living transmission and social adaptation" (Dundes, 1964, p. 256). This proposition is directly applicable to the analysis of musical performance, where each performance appears not as a copy of the previous one, but as a reconstruction of meaning in a given social situation.

Modern ethnomusicology is a multi-layered discipline, where feminist ethnomusicology also emerged in the second half of the 20th century, which reconsidered the creative role of women and the influence of gender relations on musical thinking, considering music as a means of expressing identity and power relations.

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